

Computed Tomography (CT) Scan

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Abstract

Computed Tomography (CT) scanning, first performed in 1971 by Godfrey Hounsfield and James Ambrose, marked a major advancement in medical imaging. CT is a computerized X-ray technique that produces detailed cross-sectional images, or slices, of the body, allowing visualization of bones, blood vessels, and soft tissues with greater detail than standard X-rays. The CT system includes key components such as the filter, collimator, detector array, and gantry, each contributing to image accuracy and radiation dose control. During a CT scan, a rotating X-ray source and detectors work together to generate two-dimensional slices that can be digitally combined into three-dimensional representations. The use of contrast agents, such as iodine-based or barium-based compounds, enhances image clarity for specific organs or systems. While CT scans play an essential role in diagnosis and treatment planning, they also involve exposure to ionizing radiation, presenting a small but potential biological risk.

Introduction

The first CT scan was performed in 1971 by Godfrey Hounsfield and James Ambrose, marking the beginning of modern medical imaging. Over time, CT technology evolved from slow, single-slice head scans to today's ultra-fast, high-resolution, low-dose systems [1]. Computed tomography (CT), also known as a CT scan, uses X-ray techniques to create detailed cross-sectional images, or slices, of the body. These images provide more information than standard X-rays and are used to diagnose diseases or injuries and to plan medical, surgical, or radiation treatments [2].

What is a computed tomography (CT) scan?

The term “computed tomography” (CT) describes a computerized x-ray imaging technique in which a narrow x-ray beam is directed at the patient and rapidly rotated around the body. The resulting signals are processed by the computer to create cross-sectional images, or “slices.” These tomographic images provide more detailed information than standard x-rays. When multiple consecutive slices are gathered, they can be digitally combined to produce a three-dimensional (3D) image of the patient, making it easier to identify structures and detect possible tumors or abnormalities [3].

CT equipment

Fig 1 CT Components

Filter

A filter is positioned between the x-ray source and the patient, similar to the one used in standard film radiography [4].

Fig 2 The x-ray beam intensity through a filter

A CT filter removes low-energy X-rays that increase patient dose without improving image quality, creating a narrower, more monochromatic beam for accurate reconstruction. Some scanners use shaped filters, like the bow-tie filter, to balance beam intensity across the body, with different shapes used for different body parts [4].

Collimator

The collimator is positioned between the filter and the patient. It helps reduce the patient's radiation exposure. It limits scattered radiation originating from areas outside the intended image slice [4].

Fig 3 Shows the Collimator of a CT machine

Detector Array

Early single-slice CT scanners were equipped with only one row of detectors. Modern multi-slice scanners now feature between 8 and 64 rows of detectors, with each row typically containing 1,000 to 2,000 individual detector elements [4].

Gantry

A slip-ring allows the CT scanner gantry to rotate continuously. Brushes located on the rotating gantry make contact with the stationary ring, enabling the transfer of electrical power to the gantry and the transmission of data signals to the computer. The typical rotation time of the gantry ranges from 0.25 to 3 seconds [4].

How does CT work?

Unlike a standard x-ray, which uses a stationary x-ray tube, a CT scanner employs a motorized x-ray source that rotates around the circular opening of a donut-shaped structure known as the gantry. During a CT scan, the patient lies on a motorized table that slowly moves through the gantry as the rotating x-ray tube emits narrow beams of x-rays through the body. Instead of traditional film, CT scanners use specialized digital x-ray detectors positioned opposite the x-ray source. As the x-rays exit the patient's body, they are captured by the detectors and transmitted to a computer for processing.

Each time the x-ray source completes a full rotation, the CT computer applies advanced mathematical algorithms to create a two-dimensional image slice of the body. The thickness of these slices varies depending on the scanner, typically ranging from 1 to 10 millimeters. After each slice is completed, it is stored, and the bed advances slightly through the gantry to capture the next section. This process repeats until the necessary number of slices has been obtained.

The resulting image slices can be viewed separately or digitally combined to form a three-dimensional (3D) image of the patient, displaying bones, organs, and tissues, as well as any abnormalities under investigation. This technique offers

several benefits, such as the ability to rotate the 3D image or view slices sequentially, allowing for easier localization of potential medical issues [3].

CT contrast agent

As with all X-rays, dense structures in the body, such as bone, are easily visualized, while soft tissues differ in their ability to absorb X-rays and may therefore appear faint or difficult to distinguish. For this reason, CT contrast agents have been developed that are highly visible on X-ray or CT images and are safe for patient use. These contrast agents contain substances that can absorb X-rays, making them more visible in the resulting image. For example, to examine the circulatory system, an iodine-based intravenous (IV) contrast agent is injected into the bloodstream to highlight blood vessels and detect possible blockages, including those in the heart. Oral contrast agents, such as barium-based compounds, are used to image the digestive system, including the esophagus, stomach, and gastrointestinal (GI) tract [3].

CT Risks

CT scans can diagnose serious conditions such as hemorrhage, blood clots, or cancer, and early detection can be lifesaving. However, because CT uses X-rays that produce ionizing radiation, there is a potential risk of biological effects that increases with repeated exposure, though the overall risk of developing cancer remains small [3].

Conclusion

Computed Tomography (CT) has evolved into a vital diagnostic tool that provides detailed and accurate images of internal body structures. Its ability to generate cross-sectional and three-dimensional images greatly assists in detecting abnormalities and planning medical or surgical interventions. The use of filters, collimators, detectors, and contrast agents ensures precise imaging while managing patient safety. Although CT scans expose patients to ionizing radiation, the diagnostic benefits significantly outweigh the potential risks when used appropriately.

References

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